

MUNICIPAL BODIES OF CITIZENS AND THEIR ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: There are many countries in the world, systems and management methods can be different or close to each other accordingly. The reason for this is simple. Currently, many countries in the world are democracies, and this is achieved through constitutions that comply with internationally recognized rights and laws. In particular, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was created by studying the constitutions of many developed democracies of the world and adapting it to the conditions of our country. But at the same time, it should be noted separately that some situations that do not appear in the constitution of any country are mentioned separately in our constitution.

Key words: Constitution, democracy, republic, institution, state body mahalla, municipal bodies, chairman of mahalla.

Municipal bodies of citizens are one of the means of citizens' direct implementation of public power, direct participation in state and community affairs. Its main task is to ensure that citizens are independent in solving issues of local importance.[2]

The Constitution of the Republic and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens" specify the legal status of self-governing bodies of citizens. According to this law, we can include the following in the self-government bodies of citizens, for example: a meeting of citizens of a town, village, as well as citizens of a neighborhood in a city, town, village, and village; council of citizens' assembly; commissions on the main directions of the activities of the citizens' assembly; inspection commission of citizens' assembly; administrative commission, established in the cases provided for by law, in towns, villages and farms located far from the district center and difficult to manage, etc.

Self-government bodies of citizens do not belong to the system of local state authorities. Self-government bodies of citizens enjoy the rights of a legal entity, have a model seal and must be registered with local government authorities. If you pay attention, that is the most interesting part of the matter. Because if this body exercises local state power, it would not be a self-governing subject, therefore, this body has been given the status of a legal entity, and this body functions like a public association. Only in some cases, different aspects of community association are manifested and their rights are expanded.

More than 10,000 citizens' self-government bodies operate in Uzbekistan. The election of citizens' assembly bodies and their officials is carried out by secret or open voting on the basis of general, equal and direct suffrage, ensuring the guarantees of citizens' electoral rights established by law. The law "On the election of the chairman (elder) of the citizens' assembly and his advisers"[3] was adopted to regulate activities in the relevant field.

The Citizens' Assembly is the highest body of citizens' self-governance, which has the rights to represent and protect the interests of the population, to make decisions on behalf of the

population of the territory in which it is empowered, and to communicate with state bodies on their behalf. People who have reached the age of 18 and live permanently in the territory of a town, village, village and neighborhood will participate in the citizens' meeting. The new version of the law "On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens"[4] specifies the powers of the town, village, village assembly of citizens and the assembly of citizens of the neighborhood in the city. In order to implement the decisions of the citizens' meeting and to carry out the current activities of the citizens' self-government bodies during the interim period of the citizens' meetings, the council of the citizens' meeting will be formed, consisting of the chairman (elder) of the citizens' meeting, his advisers, the chairmen of the commissions on the main directions of the activities of the citizens' meeting, and the responsible secretary of the meeting.

Organization of the activities of citizens' self-government bodies is carried out by its council and the chairman (elder) of the citizens' assembly. The Council of Citizens' Assembly may have its office, the number of its employees is determined by the assembly. It is envisaged that the chairman (elder) of the citizens' meeting, the responsible secretary and the employees of the council's office will be provided at the expense of the funds of the citizens' meeting, and in the event of a delay established by law, at the expense of the local budget. Inspection commission. It is created to check the financial and economic activities of self-governing bodies of citizens. The administrative commission will be established to review cases within the scope of its authority regarding administrative offenses and violations of the law.

In order to coordinate the activities of citizens' self-governance bodies, the Republican Council of Elders, as well as regional, district, and city coordination councils for citizens' self-governance, can be established, and this situation is usually considered a positive tool that helps to manage and regulate this area. . The financial basis of the activities of self-governing bodies of citizens is based on their own funds, budget funds allocated by the district and city councils of people's deputies in accordance with the established procedure, voluntary donations of legal entities and individuals, as well as other funds provided for by law will be available.[5]

Improving the legal basis of the activities of citizens' self-governance bodies is a demand of the times. From the first days of independence, our country followed the path of independent development based on the establishment of a democratic state and a strong civil society.

In this regard, adherence to the principle "From a strong state to a strong civil society" allowed civil society institutions to function effectively. Especially in the last decade, various institutions of civil society, non-governmental non-commercial organizations were formed and developed in all respects.

President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's speech at the joint meeting of the Legislative Chamber and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis on November 12 last year on "The concept of deepening democratic reforms and development of civil society in our country". He set new tasks for the establishment of civil society. Society In particular, the initiative of the head of our state to amend and add to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens" is aimed at further development of civil society institutions, their state power and serves to create favorable conditions for strengthening social cooperation with management bodies and expanding active participation.[6]

It should be noted that in the past period, the unique traditions and values of our people, a unique form of self-management, made a great contribution to the development of the

community, which guarantees the fulfillment of its obligations to the society. It happened Aimed at the formation of civil society. Today, as we observe the development of self-government (neighborhood) of about ten thousand citizens in our country and its strong legal base, we witness the consistent implementation of the main principle of large-scale democratic reforms in our country.

In particular, in the early years of independence, the neighborhood was given the legal authority to perform two tasks, but today more than 30 social and economic tasks have been transferred to it by the local authorities. For example, the micro district ensures peace and tranquility in its territory by providing practical assistance in solving social problems, providing public services, strengthening the family institution and ensuring its well-being. The use of effective mechanisms such as the Reconciliation Commission and the Neighborhood Service are yielding positive results.

In a sense, the neighborhood is like a big family, and therefore, conflicts, competition, mutual misunderstanding, opposition, etc. may arise in each family. But if all these secondary, random moments are eliminated, such neighborhoods are characterized by real democracy, justice, human gratitude and mutual assistance. All this leaves a deep mark on the minds and hearts of young people.

In the name of his upbringing in the neighborhood, it is not carried out in a chaotic manner. The main advantage of this is the stability of public opinion, the continuity of generations, and the living example of elders, careful treatment of a particular person, care and support for the weak (widows, orphans, disabled, lonely senior citizens) support based. After we gained independence, the status of the neighborhood increased significantly. He was given important additional tasks.

More attention was paid to educational work, especially to the young generation. With the efforts of neighborhood committees and activists, various clearly oriented educational activities were held. "The neighborhood system is the most important and supporting link of our society. In the last three years, a number of practical works on its development have been carried out. In particular, 38 laws and regulatory documents related to neighborhood institutions were adopted, more than 50 were improved. Employees of the industry who showed dedication in the life of the society were awarded with state awards. The monthly salary of the chairmen and secretaries of citizens' gatherings was increased by 1.5 times last year.

In the last three years, 624 neighborhood assembly offices were built anew, and 2,265 were reconstructed. "Neighborhood Center" buildings have been erected in 102 districts and city centers. At every citizen's meeting, "Counseling for the elderly" groups, libraries and similar institutions that are very useful for the population were organized in more than 4,000 neighborhood buildings. Thanks to the support of local activists, responsible organizations, state bodies, and the fair, pro-people policy in our country, about 87,000 low-income families have been removed from the level of need in the last three years." Formation and development of a civil society based on the gradual and consistent implementation of the principle "from a strong state to a strong civil society", the self-management of citizens - the experience of the neighborhood of Uzbekistan is of great interest, and from it in countries that are on the road to democracy can be used effectively. [7]

In addition, it is an important task to elect the persons who will carry out its activities or, if not, manage it, to a body that has a wide range of powers and a strong sphere of influence among the population.

In short, it is difficult to imagine the New Uzbekistan, which is being built in harmony with national traditions and values, without the neighborhood or, if not, the neighborhood assembly, which is the self-governing body of citizens.

The further development of this institution will bring enormous benefits to the development and progress of our country and make its indispensable, worthy contribution, based on national values, but at the same time it will develop in line with the times and grow with it, adapting to local conditions. It is not wrong to say that it forms the basis of civil society.

Therefore, taking into account the above, we should deeply understand the place and role of this body in our lives and work together for its development. Only then will we be able to achieve our highest goal and strengthen our country's independence and take its place in the world community to higher levels.

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